

PRIME PETE

PRIMARY EDUCATION PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION

Primary Physical Education Teacher Profile

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Technical sheet

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For further information on the PRIME PETE Project please follow the link:

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1. Background

One of the main features of quality education systems is that the educational content of each subject is conveyed by professionally trained teachers. Quality physical education (QPE)¹ as part of the education system also requires well-prepared teachers at every school level.

To provide QPE in primary schools, subject-related knowledge, skills, and competencies are required from every teacher teaching physical education.

The PRIME-PETE project aims to define the profile of a PE teacher: generalist or specialist.

EU countries' policies show a high degree of diversity in teaching PE in schools. Specialist PE teachers are common in upper primary grades in many EU countries, but in general preschool and lower primary grades, generalists are mainly responsible for PE. It should be noted, in some countries, only a physical education teacher (specialist) can teach the subject (e.g. Spain), while in other countries (e.g. Hungary) both the generalist and specialist teachers can teach PE and in many countries only generalist teachers can teach PE (e.g. Portugal). The situation where only generalist teachers can teach PE has led to the growing prevalence of external providers (e.g. coaches) teaching PE in some schools.

In recent decades, there have been many and continuous criticisms about the quality of primary physical education. Research studies have continuously raised questions regarding primary physical education, often critical of the quality of physical education taught by generalist teachers.^{2,3,4} Teachers may not always have the preparation necessary to teach PE given the demands of teaching many other subjects. The most prevalent problem is the limitations of the teacher preparation programs, often the insufficient number of PE-related modules⁵. Some

¹ McLennan, N., & Thompson, J. (2015). Quality physical education (QPE): Guidelines for policy makers. UNESCO Publishing.

² DeCorby, K., Halas, J., Dixon, S., Wintrup, L., & Janzen, H. (2005). Generalists and the challenges of delivering quality physical education. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 98(4), 208-221.

³ Morgan, P., & Hansen, V. (2007). Recommendations to improve primary school physical education: Generalists' perspective. *The journal of educational research*, 101(2), 99-108.

⁴ Fletcher, T., & Mandigo, J. (2012). The primary schoolteacher and physical education: a review of research and implications for Irish physical education. *Irish Educational Studies*, 31(3), 363-376.

⁵ North Western Counties Physical Education Association. (2014). World-wide survey of school physical education. UNESCO Publishing.

important associations (EUPEA, AIESEP, UNESCO) also confirm the need of QPE at the primary school level.

Positions statements - For the support of quality PE

The AIESEP published a “Position Statement on Physical Education Teacher Education”⁶ in 2014. *“AIESEP contends that physical education modules should be mandatory for all preservice generalists. These courses should allow them opportunities to understand the important role and contribution of motivated and enthusiastic teachers of primary physical education. Further engagement in physical education related content should be undertaken by all pre-service generalists through integrated modules where physical education is linked with other subjects and consideration is given to the holistic development of the child. Allocation of time for treatment of content and pedagogy needs careful attention to ensure that pre-service generalists can engage meaningfully with physical education. It is important that time for physical education, and for the practice of teaching physical education, is allocated in each year of a program.”* (pp.3)

An important position statement was published in 2015 by the EU HEPA Expert Group⁷.

“Recommendation 13 – Qualified and specialised PE teachers should be preferred at all educational levels. When not possible, as a core, qualified PE teachers or certified coaches should counsel and support general teachers.” (pp.14)

2. Development of the Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP)

2.1. Introduction

To our knowledge, no precise common profile for Primary PE teachers exists in Europe in the field of PE. As the situation regarding the implementation of Primary PE in Europe is very diverse (PE specialist teachers, generalist teachers with or without specialization in PE), the definition of a

⁶ <https://aiesep.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/2014-AIESEP-Position-Statement-on-Physical-Education-Teacher-Education.pdf>

⁷ Expert Group on Health Enhancing Physical Activity (2015): Recommendations to Encourage Physical Education in Schools, Including Motor Skills in Early Childhood, and to Create Valuable Interactions with the Sport Sector, Local Authorities and the Private Sector. Available online: <https://www.sportetcitoyennete.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Expert-Group-Recommendations-to-encourage-physical-education-in-schools.pdf>

common, reliable profile is challenging. Nevertheless, a profile with core competency requirements (core of the curriculum) for the implementation of QPE in primary schools is necessary and would be helpful to orientate Primary PETE curriculum development in general.

To raise the quality of PE and its teaching in primary schools, a two-level descriptor system of teacher competency requirements (core and extended dimensions) could be considered an interesting support. Developing a Primary Physical Education Teacher Profile (PPETP) is an important part of the work of the PRIME-PETE project.

Earlier work (intellectual output #1 (IO#1) and intellectual output#2 (IO#2) of the PRIME-PETE project informed the development of the PPETP.

Concerning IO#1, the project partners collected data according to the following criteria:

- Existing profiles for Primary Education teachers teaching PE in Europe.
- Existing concepts, models, and curricula for Primary PETE in Europe.
- Existing links to European frameworks, e.g. the European Qualification Framework (EQF).

IO#1 resulted in (1) a presentation of an overview of primary education PE teacher education in Europe, (2) a review of literature related to Primary PE Teacher Education, and (3) a Delphi consensus study that investigated aspects of knowledge, skills, and wider competencies for teaching quality PE

Concerning IO#2, the project partners carried out a mapping and exchange of the primary PETE course modules they are offering in current programs at their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), focusing on the following aspects:

- Course modules in existing programs for specialist primary education PE teachers.
- Course modules in existing programs for generalist primary education PE teachers (including those with specialism / additional PE modules).

For the development of Intellectual output #3 (IO#3), the following steps have been taken:

- Analysis of the outputs of IO#1 and IO#2 documents.
- Derivation of implications and conclusions for the development of PPETP.
- Identification of core and extended competency requirements of primary education PE teachers for the implementation of QPE.

The aims of the output IO#3 of the PRIME-PETE project are

1. to develop the primary PE teacher profile (core and extended competences requirement – for teachers teaching PE.)
2. to identify conclusions to inform the development of a theoretical and methodological framework for primary Physical Education Teacher Education (IO#4).

2.2. The Framework of the PPETP – the CALOHEE2 and the PRIME-PETE Delphi study

Two key elements informed the development of the framework for the PPETP: CALOHEE2 TUNING (Qualifications Reference Framework of General Descriptors in the Subject Area of Teacher Education, 2018⁸) and the PRIME-PETE Delphi study.

This work offers a platform for debate and reflection, as well as comparison and benchmarking of Teacher Education programs, fostering quality improvement and graduates who are competent and confident.

The CALOHEE2 Project

The CALOHEE2 project developed a ‘meta-profile’ of the general teacher education (not specific to PE) based on the work of expert academics in consultation with students and other stakeholders.

The descriptors in the Qualifications Reference Framework are organized based on ‘dimensions’ and each dimension contains ‘subdimensions’. Six dimensions provided the first structure for our proposed system:

Dimension 1: Knowledge management and creation

Dimension 2: Design and management of processes of learning, teaching, and assessment

Dimension 3: Learner empowerment, potential, and creativity

⁸ <https://www.calohee.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/1.2-Guidelines-and-Reference-Points-for-the-Design-and-Delivery-of-Degree-Programmes-in-Teacher-Education-FINAL-v2.pdf>

Dimension 4: Communication

Dimension 5: Values and social leadership

Dimension 6: Development as professionals and life-long learners

Each of the dimensions comprises three descriptors – knowledge, skills and autonomy, and responsibility (‘wider competencies’) which reflect the European Qualification Framework⁹.

PRIME-PETE DELPHI: the development of the Dimensions for the PPETP

The PRIME-PETE Delphi consensus study aimed to adapt and reword each of the CALOHEE2 dimensions and statements to a PETE-specific content. A group of project internal (PRIME-PETE experts) and external experts (Expert Advisory Group) were asked to suggest contents (statements) for each of the dimensions and subdimensions.

Based on the results of the Delphi consensus study, the PRIME-PETE dimensions are identified in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Original CALOHEE2 dimensions and their modification to the PRIME-PETE project

ORIGINAL CALOHEE2 DIMENSIONS	PRIME-PETE DIMENSIONS
DIMENSION 1. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND CREATION	DIMENSION 1. KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT
DIMENSION 2. DESIGN AND MANAGEMENT OF PROCESSES OF LEARNING, TEACHING AND ASSESSMENT	DIMENSION 2. TEACHING, LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT
DIMENSION 3.	DIMENSION 3.

⁹ Union, C. E. (2017). Council Recommendation, of 22 May 2017, on the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning and Repealing the Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2008 on the Establishment of the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 15-28.

LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL AND CREATIVITY: Supporting learner holistic growth and development	LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL, DIVERSITY AND CREATIVITY
DIMENSION 4. VALUES AND SOCIAL LEADERSHIP: Ethics and social commitment	DIMENSION 4. VALUES, SOCIAL LEADERSHIP AND COMMUNICATION
DIMENSION 5. COMMUNICATION: Communication with different actors and in different contexts	
DIMENSION 6. DEVELOPMENT AS PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS	DIMENSION 5. DEVELOPMENT AS REFLECTIVE PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS

2.3. The PRIME-PETE DELPHI: The development of the statements for the PPETP

During the first round, the national panel experts formulated 42 statements for Knowledge, 38 statements for Skills, and 29 for Wider Competencies (109 in total) in all dimensions as a starting point for generating consensus on the most important descriptors. After the final (3rd) round, significant reductions were apparent in all dimensions. Finally, only one statement for Knowledge, 13 for Skills, and 10 for Wider Competencies (24 in total) were above the predefined statistical threshold (85%). From these 24 statements, the three top-ranked descriptors in each dimension are listed below (13 in total):

Dimension 1.

- Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills.
- Knowledge about children's overall development.
- Knowledge of PA recommendations for children and young people.

Dimension 2.

- Ability to plan and teach QPE lessons.

- Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment.
- Ability to plan long-term and short-term PE programs based on students' developmental level and readiness.

Dimension 3.

- Capacity and commitment to supporting the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels.
- Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment.
- Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence.

Dimension 4.

- Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students.
- Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and non-verbally.
- Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting.

Dimension 5¹⁰.

- Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for PE in the school and beyond.

Building on the 5 dimensions and 13 statements listed in Table 2, the PRIME-PETE partners added 17 further statements for the core competency requirements based on experts' agreement (30 final statements altogether). These statements are now represented in the Tables 3 and 4 (Descriptive matrix of PRIME-PETE Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP) – core level PPETP. The matrix shows how many statements constitute each dimension.

Furthermore, the PRIME-PETE partners agreed to develop the extended level competency requirements for the PPETP. In this development, the experts added 36 more statements in knowledge, skill and wider competency to the system. These 66 statements constitute the extended PPETP (table 4 and 5 - Descriptive matrix of PRIME-PETE Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP).

¹⁰ (only 1 statement was above the threshold)

What is the PPETP?

The PPETP is the description of a primary PE teacher profile. This can provide a strong basis for further work in primary PE teacher education including the development of policies related to primary PE and teacher education programs. Furthermore, it can act as a critical point of reference for primary PE student teachers, sporting organizations, and beyond¹¹.

The list of dimensions and statements altogether constitutes a profile that can guide the development of learning outcomes for undergraduate and postgraduate teacher education in the future.

By outlining the key elements in PPETP, the profile aims to serve as a checklist for existing teacher education programs and a guideline for those still being developed. This checklist constitutes a way to compare the dimensions of the profile suggested in the project PRIME-PETE and the reality of the partner's institutions profile.

¹¹ It should be noted, all the statements are applies to physical education context.

3. PRIME-PETE – Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP core level)

The following section details the system of PRIME-PETE – Primary PE Teacher Profile at a core level. In table 2., a descriptive matrix is showing, how many statements are constituting each dimension. The following tables are containing all requirements in each dimension.

Table 2: Descriptive matrix of PRIME-PETE Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP) – core level.

Dimension	Knowledge	Skills	Autonomy and responsibility (wider competences)	TOTAL
D1	4	3	1	8
D2	1	5	0	6
D3	1	2	3	6
D4	1	3	3	7
D5	0	0	3	3
TOTAL	7	13	10	30

Table 3: Requirements in the PRIME-PETE Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP) – core level

Dimension 1: KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D1K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills	D1S1 Ability to use basic educational research, and applying existing theories and educational methods, to enhance teaching	D1C1 Capacity and autonomy to modify and adapt core educational and curricular policies to pedagogical practice
D1K2 Knowledge about children’s overall development	D1S2 Ability to arrange pedagogical work in line with policies of an education system and educational theories	
D1K3 Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people	D1S3 Ability to use evidence-based educational theories and practices and ignore pseudoscientific claims and programmes	
D1K4 Knowledge and understanding of the cultures of physical activity, physical education, and sport		

Dimension 2: TEACHING, LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D2K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding for cross-thematic and interdisciplinary teaching in physical education	D2S1 Ability to plan and teach quality physical education lessons	
	D2S2 Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment	
	D2S3 Ability to plan long-term and short-term physical education programmes based on students’ developmental level and readiness	
	D2S4 Ability to demonstrate correctly, or provide a correct demonstration through a third party, of all major skills and tactics central to the relevant curriculum	
	D2S5 Ability to using digital technology for learning and assessment	

Dimension 3: LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL, DIVERSITY AND CREATIVITY		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D3K1 Advanced knowledge of inclusion principles and practices	D3S1 Ability to support learners in identifying own strengths and setting goals to build on these	D3C1 Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels
	D3S2 Ability to work together with special education professionals, and adapt learning tasks to the individual needs of the students	D3C2 Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment
		D3C3 Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence

Dimension 4: VALUES, SOCIAL LEADERSHIP AND COMMUNICATION		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D4K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding as to how physical activity can be promoted in the whole-school context	D4S1 Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and nonverbally	D4C1 Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students
	D4S2 Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting	D4C2 Capacity and commitment to respect different values, when interacting with people in contexts of diversity (social, ethnic, economic, political) and learn from that diversity
	D4S3 Ability to reflect on personal capacity, qualities and competencies as a subject leader in physical education	D4C3 Capacity and commitment to adhere to children’s rights

Dimension 5: DEVELOPMENT AS REFLECTIVE PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
		D5C1 Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for physical education in the school and beyond
		D5C2 Capacity and commitment to make use of colleagues, professional organisations and resources to develop as a reflective practitioner
		D5C3 Capacity and commitment to “cultural literacy” to support students coming from other cultures

The PRIME-PETE projects is developing Profiles for generalist PE teachers and specialist PE teachers. As the Specialist benefits for more time for the PE education, the profile may be also wider.

4. PRIME-PETE – Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP –extended level)

The following section details the system of PRIME-PETE – Primary PE Teacher Profile at extended level. In table 4, a descriptive matrix is showing, how many statements are constituting each dimension. The following tables are containing all the requirements in each dimension. The system includes the core level statements (white background), and the extended level statements (green background).

Table 4: Descriptive matrix of PRIME-PETE Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP) –extended level

Dimension	Knowledge	Skills	Autonomy and responsibility (wider competences)	TOTAL
D1	7	3	4	14
D2	5	8	3	16
D3	4	6	3	13
D4	2	5	6	13
D5	1	3	6	10
TOTAL	19	25	22	66

Table 5: Requirements in the PRIME-PETE Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP) – core level in white , extended level in green

Dimension 1: KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D1K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills	D1S1 Ability to use basic educational research, and applying existing theories and educational methods, to enhance teaching	D1C1 Capacity and autonomy to modify and adapt core educational and curricular policies to pedagogical practice
D1K2 Knowledge about children’s overall development	D1S2 Ability to arrange pedagogical work in line with policies of an education system and educational theories	
D1K3 Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people	D1S3 Ability to use evidence-based educational theories and practices and ignore pseudoscientific claims and programmes	
D1K4 Knowledge and understanding of the cultures of physical activity, physical education, and sport		
D1K5 Advanced knowledge and understanding of holistic and learner-focused educational approaches to physical education and health education		D1C2 Capacity and responsibility to integrate key competency development to the physical education programme
D1K6 Advanced knowledge and understanding of the role and significance of the body as a means of creative expression and artistic communication through exploration of a wide range of content within physical education		D1C3 Capacity and commitment to using physical education specific concepts and terminology appropriately
D1K7 Advanced knowledge and critical understanding of sociological, philosophical, psychological and pedagogical theories in education and physical education		D1C4 Capacity and commitment to critically reflect on educational policies

Dimension 2: TEACHING, LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D2K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding for cross-thematic and interdisciplinary teaching in physical education	D2S1 Ability to plan and teach quality physical education lessons	
	D2S2 Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment	
	D2S3 Ability to plan long-term and short-term physical education programmes based on students' developmental level and readiness	
	D2S4 Ability to demonstrate correctly, or provide a correct demonstration through a third party, of all major skills and tactics central to the relevant curriculum	
	D2S5 Ability to using digital technology for learning and assessment	
D2K2 Advanced knowledge of group dynamics (including conflict management) and student-centered strategies	D2S6 Ability to promote efficient use of movement time	D2C1 Capacity and commitment to cooperate with other teachers and develop school curricula based on reflection
D2K3 Advanced knowledge of the national curriculum	D2S7 Ability to use observation, self- and peer-assessment in physical education lessons and programmes	D2C2 Capacity and commitment to using different teaching strategies and model-based teaching in physical education lessons
D2K4 Advanced knowledge and understanding of different motor learning theories, and typical and atypical motor development, and practical consequences	D2S8 Ability to use teaching skills to support learning in different learning environments	D2C3 Analyse and critique playgrounds, outdoor areas and parks as places for learning in physical education
D2K5 Advanced knowledge on how to measure, reflect and evaluate physical education programmes		

Dimension 3: LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL, DIVERSITY AND CREATIVITY		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D3K1 Advanced knowledge of inclusion principles and practices	D3S1 Ability to support learners in identifying own strengths and setting goals to build on these	D3C1 Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels
	D3S2 Ability to work together with special education professionals, and adapt learning tasks to the individual needs of the students	D3C2 Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment
		D3C3 Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence
D3K2 Advanced knowledge and commitment to the application of the concept of the student as an active learner, thinker, mover and problem solver engaging with the content of the physical education curriculum	D3S3 Ability to build upon students' previous experiences, active participation, and creativity	
D3K3 Advanced knowledge and understanding to recognise and differentiate healthy competitive and non-competitive concepts	D3S4 Ability to design autonomy supported learning environment, and mastery learning	
D3K4 Advanced knowledge of school counseling processes and of how to advise students (and their families/guardians) to develop learners' resources	D3S5 Ability to motivate students to practice sport activities in collaboration with peers, families and sport coaches	
	D3S6 Ability to support students learning through an examination of a range of resources and equipment related to teaching physical education	

Dimension 4: VALUES, SOCIAL LEADERSHIP AND COMMUNICATION		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
D4K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding as to how physical activity can be promoted in the whole-school context	D4S1 Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and nonverbally	D4C1 Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students
	D4S2 Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting	D4C2 Capacity and commitment to respect different values, when interacting with people in contexts of diversity (social, ethnic, economic, political) and learn from that diversity
	D4S3 Ability to reflect on personal capacity, qualities and competencies as a subject leader in physical education	D4C3 Capacity and commitment to adhere to children's rights
D4K2 Advanced knowledge of ethical and professional standards, including knowledge about the constitution of appropriate relationships with learners	D4S4 Ability to create situations for recognising and understanding fair-play	D4C4 Capacity and commitment to take responsibility to promote and/or initiate teamwork among learners
	D4S5 Ability to organise extracurricular activities, and other educational events in response to social need	D4C5 Capacity and commitment to work with external providers to support learning in physical education
		D4C6 Capacity and commitment to promoting responsible and critical use of social media and communication technologies among learners

Dimension 5: DEVELOPMENT AS REFLECTIVE PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS		
KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
		D5C1 Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for physical education in the school and beyond
		D5C2 Capacity and commitment to make use of colleagues, professional organisations and resources to develop as a reflective practitioner
		D5C3 Capacity and commitment to “cultural literacy” to support students coming from other cultures
D5K1 Advanced knowledge of main sources of information that permit teachers to stay updated with general and physical education-related educational research and developments	D5S1 Ability to critically examine educational research and developments (publications, events, resources, etc.) in search of solutions for challenges experienced in own classroom	D5C4 Capacity and commitment to critically reflect and work on consistency of own personal and professional identity
	D5S2 Ability to develop adequate coping strategies, social support or preventive identification and influencing of stressors in the private and professional context	D5C5 Capacity and commitment to identify opportunities for collaboration and professional dialogue where teachers can develop networks, undertake peer observations and engage in collaborative professional learning
	D5S3 Ability to promote health and wellbeing concept by supporting active reflection about their job	D5C6 Capacity and commitment to ongoing professional development through the design of a professional development plan to guide growth as a physical education teacher

5. Conclusions

The development of a PPETP to guide development of teacher education programmes constitutes a significant step in promoting teaching of quality PE in primary schools across Europe and beyond. It is important to consider that preparation of generalist teachers includes modules grounded in humanities, sociology, pedagogy and didactics as part of the core work for student primary education teachers. Hence, rather than repeating these elements the focus in the development of the PPETP is on building on these elements and adapting them to the teaching of physical education. The dimensions outlined within the profile are designed to provide guidance for both generalists and specialists across dimensions that are identified as 'core dimensions' and further dimensions described as 'extended dimensions'.

IO#4 will provide a theoretical and methodological framework for primary PETE to develop content presented as exemplar material in the form of modules and micro-modules. The framework and exemplar content are informed by the dimensions outlined in the PPETP. Informed by the framework, engagement with the content should result in confident teachers motivated to create a safe and positive environment to facilitate learning by the child. In turn, this learning across the four dimensions – also consistent in physical literacy (physical, emotional, social and cognitive) can lead to children acquiring and maintaining an active and healthy lifestyle.

To inform the development of a theoretical and methodological framework for primary Physical Education Teacher Education (IO#4) and develop adapted PRIME PETE Curriculum (IO#5) the project offers material and tools for physical education teacher's education (generalists and specialists).

6. Bibliography

- AIESEP (2015) Position statement on Physical Education <https://aiesep.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/2014-AIESEP-Position-Statement-on-Physical-Education-Teacher-Education.pdf>
- DeCorby, K., Halas, J., Dixon, S., Wintrup, L., & Janzen, H. (2005). Generalists and the challenges of delivering quality physical education. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 98(4), 208-221.
- Expert Group on Health Enhancing Physical Activity (2015): Recommendations to Encourage Physical Education in Schools, Including Motor Skills in Early Childhood, and to Create Valuable Interactions with the Sport Sector, Local Authorities and the Private Sector. Available online: <https://www.sportetcityennete.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Expert-Group-Recommendations-to-encourage-physical-education-in-schools.pdf>
- Fletcher, T., & Mandigo, J. (2012). The primary schoolteacher and physical education: a review of research and implications for Irish physical education. *Irish Educational Studies*, 31(3), 363-376.
- Griggs & Randall, 2018; Randall, V., Richardson, A., Swaithe, W. and Adams, A. (2016) *Generation Next: The preparation of pre-service teachers in primary physical education* Winchester: University of Winchester
- Kaunonen, M., Gobbi, M., Meier, K., Østergaard, B., Nielsen, D. S., Kollak, I., ... & McCready, I. (2018). Tuning educational structures in Europe: Guidelines and reference points for the design and delivery of degree programmes in nursing. *Tuning educational structures in Europe*. University of Groningen. <https://www.calohee.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/1.2-Guidelines-and-Reference-Points-for-the-Design-and-Delivery-of-Degree-Programmes-in-Teacher-Education-FINAL-v2.pdf>
- McLennan, N., & Thompson, J. (2015). *Quality physical education (QPE): Guidelines for policy makers*. UNESCO Publishing.
- Morgan, P., & Hansen, V. (2007). Recommendations to improve primary school physical education: Generalists' perspective. *The journal of educational research*, 101(2), 99-108.
- North Western Counties Physical Education Association. (2014). *World-wide survey of school physical education*. UNESCO Publishing.
- Union, C. E. (2017). Council Recommendation, of 22 May 2017, on the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning and Repealing the Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2008 on the Establishment of the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 15-28. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32017H0615\(01\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32017H0615(01)&from=EN)